

COMMUNITY CAPACITY BUILDING IN PUBLIC ORDER AND PUBLIC ORDER IN AMPENAN DISTRICT, MATARAM CITY

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Abstract

This Community Service (PKM) aims to increase understanding, legal awareness, and community capacity in maintaining public order and public peace, as well as community protection (Trantibumlinmas) in Ampenan District, Mataram City. The background to this activity is based on the still low level of public understanding of regulations, the less than optimal role of the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas), and the lack of community participation in maintaining environmental security, especially in heterogeneous communities such as immigrant communities. The activity implementation method uses a participatory and educational approach through socialization, interactive discussions, community mentoring, and activity evaluation. Data collection techniques are carried out through observation, interviews, documentation, and literature studies. This activity involves the community, village officials, community leaders, youth, and Satlinmas members as the main actors in the implementation of Trantibumlinmas. The results of the activity show an increase in community understanding of the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 26 of 2020, increased legal awareness, and growing community participation in maintaining environmental order. In addition, the role of Satlinmas also shows improvements in aspects of early detection, environmental security, and social mediation at the village level. Thus, this Community Service Program (PKM) activity contributes to strengthening the synergy between the community, government, and the Public Order Agency (Satlinmas) in creating a safe, orderly, and conducive environment. The resulting recommendations include the need for continuous strengthening of the capacity of the Public Order Agency (Linmas) and an enhanced community-based participant approach to the implementation of the Public Order Agency (Trantibumlinmas).

Keywords: *Public Order Agency (Trantibumlinmas), Public Order Agency (Satlinmas), community participation, empowerment, public order*

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Maintaining public order, public safety, and community protection (Trantibumlinmas) is one of the mandatory government affairs related to basic services as mandated by Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government. Within the framework of decentralization, regional governments have a strategic responsibility to ensure social stability, create a sense of security, and maintain the quality of life for the community. Trantibumlinmas is not only understood as an effort to maintain order, but also as part of responsive, participatory, and service-oriented governance. Therefore, the effectiveness of Trantibumlinmas implementation is an important indicator in assessing the capacity of regional governments to meet the basic needs of the community in a sustainable manner. In an operational context, Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 26 of 2020 provides technical guidelines for the implementation of Trantibumlinmas (Community Protection Units), including strengthening the role of the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas) as the frontline at the village and sub-district levels. Satlinmas has a strategic function in assisting in handling disturbances to public order, mitigating social conflict, and supporting government and community activities. However, this role will not be optimal without an adequate understanding of regulations, a clear institutional structure, and adequate human resource capacity. In this

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regard, policy dissemination is a crucial instrument for transforming legal norms into effective social practices. Theoretically, strengthening Trantibumlinmas at the local level can be understood through a *public governance perspective* that emphasizes collaboration between government and society in creating public value. Ansell and Torfing (2021) emphasize that modern public governance is moving toward *co-creation*, where government and non-government actors play an active role in the process of solving public problems. This aligns with the concept of *public service logic* proposed by Osborne (2021), which positions the public as partners in the process of creating public services, not merely as objects of policy. Furthermore, digital transformation in the public sector is also driving changes in bureaucratic work patterns that are more adaptive and integrated, as expressed by Mergel et al. (2023), thus requiring strengthening institutional capacity at the local level, including in the implementation of Trantibumlinmas. However, empirical reality in the region shows that the implementation of the Trantibumlinmas policy still faces various obstacles. As academics who have the responsibility of the tridharma of higher education to provide their contributions in the form of community service through **the Socialization of the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 26 of 2020 in an effort to increase community capacity in Trantibumlinmas in Ampenan District, Mataram City**, the following is shown the population data of Ampenan District as an initial overview of the current conditions, namely as follows:

Table 1 Population of Ampenan District in 2026

No	Area code	Ward	Man	Woman	Amount
1	52.71.01.1004	South Ampenan	5,198	5,26	10,458
2	52.71.01.1005	Central Ampenan	6,048	6,076	12,124
3	52.71.01.1006	Orange	5,420	5,440	10,860
4	52.71.01.1007	North Ampenan	4,462	4,527	8,989
5	52.71.01.1008	Taman Sari	4,282	4,413	8,695
6	52.71.01.1009	Banjar	3,618	3,678	7,296
7	52.71.01.1010	Kebun Sari	4,558	4,586	9,144
8	52.71.01.1011	Spacing of Works	3,709	3,722	7,431
9	52.71.01.1012	Dayan Peken	4,413	4,520	8,933
10	52.71.01.1013	Bintaro	5,474	5,428	10,902
11	52.71.01	Ampenan District	47,182	47,65	94,832

Data source: One data of Maaram City 2026

From table 1 above, the PKM team can provide an analysis that the conditions of peace, public order, and community protection (Trantibumlinmas) in Ampenan District are influenced by demographic characteristics, population density, community socio-economic activities, and the dynamics of the rapidly developing urban area. Based on population data, Ampenan District has a total population of 94,832 people consisting of 47,182 men and 47,650 women. This number indicates that Ampenan District is one of the areas with a high level of community social activity in Mataram, thus requiring optimal and sustainable Trantibumlinmas management. Academically, a high population growth leads to increased potential disruptions to public order and security, such as social conflicts between residents, violations of environmental order, congestion in residential areas and markets, juvenile delinquency, and increased vulnerability to neighborhood-wide crime. These conditions require the active involvement of sub-district governments, security forces, and the community through strengthening community protection (Linmas) capacity and community social participation.

The most populous sub-district is Central Ampenan with a total of 12,124 residents, followed by Bintaro with 10,902 residents, Pejeruk with 10,860 residents, and South Ampenan with 10,458 residents. The high population density in these areas indicates a relatively high level of social interaction and community mobility, potentially increasing the complexity of public order and public order issues. Therefore, areas with high population densities require more intensive environmental monitoring, voluntary security systems, and stakeholder coordination. Meanwhile, sub-districts with relatively smaller populations, such as Banjar (7,296 people) and Pejarakan Karya (7,431 people), tend to have more controlled levels of social interaction, but still have the potential for social vulnerability if not balanced with community development and strengthening of Linmas institutions. From a public administration perspective, equitable distribution of neighborhood security services and increasing public legal awareness must still be carried out comprehensively, regardless of population density.

From a community protection perspective, the presence of a Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas) in each sub-district is a strategic element in supporting the maintenance of public order and security. Satlinmas not only functions to assist in handling environmental security disturbances, but also plays a role in disaster mitigation, social activities, securing public activities, and supporting the implementation of regional government. With a population of nearly 100,000 in Ampenan District, strengthening Satlinmas' capacity through training, regulatory dissemination, and improved cross-sectoral coordination is a crucial need. Furthermore, the heterogeneous social conditions of the Ampenan District community in terms of economics, culture, and trade activities also influence the dynamics of Trantibumlinmas. As an urban area and center of coastal community activity, Ampenan District has a high level of population mobility, necessitating a collaborative approach based on community participation to maintain social stability. Therefore, the implementation of Trantibumlinmas policies, as stipulated in Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 26 of 2020, needs to be participatory, adaptive, and based on local community needs. Thus, the condition of Trantibumlinmas in Ampenan District shows that the increase in population and density has a close relationship with the need to strengthen the environmental security system, community empowerment, and increase the capacity of Satlinmas to create a safe, orderly, and conducive environment. Based on the condition of peace, public order, and community protection (Trantibumlinmas) in Ampenan District which has a fairly high population and complex social dynamics of the community, the problem formulation in the activity **"Increasing Community Capacity in Trantibumlinmas in Ampenan District, Mataram City (Socialization of the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 26 of 2020)"** is as follows:

1. How can the implementation of the dissemination of the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 26 of 2020 increase the community's capacity to maintain peace, public order, and community protection?
2. What factors influence the low participation and capacity of the community in supporting the implementation of Trantibumlinmas in Ampenan District?
3. How to build synergy between the local government, Satlinmas, and the community in creating a safe, orderly, and conducive environment in Ampenan District?

1.3 Research Gap & Novelty

Numerous studies have been conducted on public order and security, particularly those related to the role of local governments, the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP), and the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas) in maintaining social stability. Most previous research has focused on the enforcement of local regulations, public order oversight, and the effectiveness of government officials in implementing public order and security. Furthermore, several studies have also highlighted the environmental security approach and community participation in maintaining social order in urban areas. However, there remains a research gap regarding strengthening community capacity in implementing Trantibumlinmas based on the socialization of regulations, particularly the implementation of Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 26 of 2020. Previous research generally has not specifically discussed how public understanding of Trantibumlinmas regulations can influence the level of community social participation in maintaining security and order in the environment. On the other hand, studies linking urban population density with the need for community capacity building in Trantibumlinmas are also relatively limited.

Another gap is the limited research focused on community empowerment approaches through legal outreach and strengthening social institutions at the sub-district and village levels. Yet, the complex social dynamics of urban communities, such as those in Ampenan District, require a collaborative approach between the government, the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas), and the community. Based on these conditions, the novelty of this activity and study lies in its approach to increasing community capacity based on the dissemination of Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 26 of 2020 as an instrument for strengthening community participation in the implementation of Trantibumlinmas (public order and public order). This activity positions the community not only as the object of policy but also as an active subject in creating peace and public order in their respective communities. Furthermore, another novelty is the integration of population density, urban social characteristics, and community empowerment into the analysis of Trantibumlinmas (Community Safety and Environment) in Ampenan District. This approach provides a new perspective, emphasizing that the success of Trantibumlinmas implementation depends not only on government officials but also on the community's social capacity to understand regulations, build collective awareness, and strengthen environmental security synergies through participatory processes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1 Concept of Public Order and Public Peace

Public order is a social condition that demonstrates the regularity of societal behavior in accordance with applicable legal and social norms. According to Soerjono Soekanto (2010), social order is a state in which interactions between individuals occur in accordance with agreed-upon norms, thereby minimizing conflict. Order is achieved when there is compliance with the law and effective social control mechanisms. Public order is related to a sense of security and comfort in social life. Satjipto Rahardjo (2009) explains that law functions to create an atmosphere of peace and justice in society. Peace is not only the absence of physical disturbance, but also the assurance of legal certainty and a sense of justice. From a public administration perspective, public order and public safety are part of the government's basic services to citizens. The government is obligated to ensure social stability as a prerequisite for development (Asshiddiqie, 2011).

2.1.2 Community Protection (Linmas)

Community protection is a systematic effort to protect citizens from the threat of disasters, security disturbances, and social conflict. This concept is rooted in the principle of human security, namely the protection of individuals from direct threats to their safety and well-being. According to Jimly Asshiddiqie (2011), the state has a constitutional responsibility to protect all Indonesians. This principle forms the basis for the formation of various legal instruments, including regulations related to community protection. In the village/sub-district context, the existence of the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas) represents a form of community participation in maintaining social stability. Satlinmas assists the village government in environmental security, disaster management, and supporting social activities.

2.1.3 Legal Theory as Social Engineering

concept of *law as a tool of social engineering* states that law serves as a means to shape and direct social change. In the Indonesian context, this idea was developed by Satjipto Rahardjo (2009) through the concept of progressive law, which positions law as an instrument for realizing social welfare and order. Thus, Home Affairs Ministerial Regulation Number 26 of 2020 can be understood as a social engineering instrument aimed at building a more structured system of public order and protection at the regional and village levels.

2.1.4 Theory of Legal Awareness

According to Soerjono Soekanto (2010), legal awareness includes four indicators:

1. Knowledge of law
2. Understanding the contents of the law
3. Attitude towards the law
4. Legal behavior patterns

Socialization of regulations is one strategy to increase public legal awareness so that regulations are not only known, but also complied with and implemented consistently.

2.2 Legalistic Study

2.2.1 Constitutional Basis

Constitutionally, community protection is part of the state's objectives as stated in the Preamble to the 1945 Constitution, namely to protect all Indonesian people and all Indonesian territory.

2.2.2 Legal Basis

1. Law Number 23 of 2014

Public Order, Public Order, and Public Protection (Trantibumlinmas) are designated as mandatory government affairs related to basic services. This authority is specifically regulated in Article 11 paragraph (2) and Article 12 paragraph (1) letter e. The following are important points regarding Trantibumlinmas' authority (Law 23/2014):

- 1) Article 11 paragraph (2): Establishes Trantibumlinmas as a mandatory government affair related to basic services.
- 2) Article 12 paragraph (1) letter e: Affirms that public order, security and community protection are part of the 6 mandatory basic services.

3) Scope (Article 12 paragraph (2)): Includes enforcement of Regional Regulations/Regional Regulations, maintenance of public order, and protection of the community.

This basic service must be implemented by regional governments (provinces and districts/cities) with SPM (Minimum Service Standards) to guarantee citizens' constitutional rights.

2. Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 26 of 2020

Concerning the Implementation of Public Order and Public Peace and Community Protection, technically regulates:

- 1) **Scope:** Regulating capacity building, formation and management of community protection units.
- 2) **Linmas Functions:** Protecting the community from security disturbances, assisting in disaster management, and maintaining public order.
- 3) **Institutions:** The formation of Satlinmas in villages is determined by the Village Head, while in sub-districts by the Regent/Mayor.
- 4) **Job Description:** Increasing the role of Linmas in social and security activities at the community level.

This regulation aims to strengthen synergy between local governments, Satpol PP, and the community in maintaining environmental order.

This Minister of Home Affairs Regulation emphasizes that Satlinmas is under the village head/sub-district head and is coordinated with Satpol PP in carrying out its duties.

3. Mataram Mayor Regulation Number 26 of 2017

Mataram Mayor Regulation Number 26 of 2017 concerning Implementation Guidelines for Mataram City Regional Regulation Number 11 of 2015 concerning Public Order and Security is a technical regulation governing the mechanism for maintaining public order and security in Mataram City. This regulation is designed as an operational guideline for the regional government, regional law enforcement officers, and the community in creating a safe, orderly, comfortable, and conducive environment. This regulation demonstrates that maintaining public order and security is not solely focused on law enforcement, but also emphasizes a preventative approach, community development, and social participation. Regional governments, through the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP), are authorized to supervise, regulate, provide guidance, and enforce regulations on various community activities that could potentially disrupt public order.

These regulations govern various aspects of social order, such as public road safety, residential areas, businesses, social activities, environmental cleanliness, and community activities that have the potential to cause social disruption. From a public administration perspective, these regulations reflect the role of local governments as regulators and facilitators in maintaining social stability in urban communities. Furthermore, this Mayoral Regulation emphasizes the importance of synergy between local governments, security forces, and the community in maintaining environmental peace. This collaborative approach is crucial because public order issues in urban areas are influenced by high levels of community mobility, economic activity, and complex social dynamics.

In the context of community protection, the implementation of Mayoral Regulation No. 26 of 2017 serves as an instrument to strengthen social oversight and increase public legal awareness of the importance of public order. This regulation also strengthens the implementation of Trantibumlinmas policies through community development, controlling disturbances, and strengthening the role of regional institutions in creating an orderly and safe social environment. Thus, Mataram Mayor Regulation Number 26 of 2017 can be understood as an implementation policy that supports the creation of responsive, participatory regional governance that is oriented towards social stability through the implementation of public order and security in an integrated manner.

2.2.3 Institutional and Governance Aspects

good governance perspective, the implementation of Trantibumlinmas must fulfill the following principles:

1. Accountability
2. Transparency
3. Community participation
4. Effectiveness and efficiency

This principle is in line with the United Nations Development Programme's (UNDP, 1997) view on good governance, where community participation is an important element in maintaining social stability.

2.3 Framework of Thought

Based on theoretical studies and legal foundations, the following framework can be prepared:

Figure 1: Framework of Thought

METHOD

3.1 Form of Activity

This Community Service (PKM) activity is implemented through outreach and education activities for the public regarding Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 26 of 2020 concerning the Implementation of Public Order and Public Tranquility, as well as Community Protection (Trantibumlinmas). This activity is aimed at increasing public understanding, legal awareness, and capacity to maintain security, order, and environmental tranquility in a participatory manner.

The implementation of activities is carried out in the form of:

1. Delivery of socialization materials related to Trantibumlinmas;
2. Education regarding the role of the community and Satlinmas;
3. Interactive discussion and Q&A;
4. Community participatory assistance;
5. Evaluate participants' understanding of the activity.

3.2 Location and Time of Implementation

PKM activities were carried out in Ampenan District, targeting the community, village officials, community leaders, youth, and members of the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas).

The time for the activity to be carried out on Thursday, April 29, 2026 in the Ampenan District Hall has been agreed upon with the local district and sub-district officials.

3.3 Activity Objectives

The targets of this PKM activity include:

1. Communities in Ampenan District;
2. Village and environmental officials;
3. Community leaders and youth leaders;
4. Members of Satlinmas;
5. Community organizations at the sub-district level.

These targets were chosen because they have a strategic role in supporting the maintenance of public order and security in the community.

3.4 Implementation Method

The method of implementing activities uses a participatory and educational approach so that the community can understand the substance of the regulations and be able to apply them in the social life of the community.

1. Lecture Method

The lecture method is used to convey material regarding:

- 1) Trantibumlinmas Concept;
- 2) The role of society in maintaining public order;
- 3) Duties and functions of Satlinmas;
- 4) Substance of the Regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs Number 26 of 2020;
- 5) Forms of community participation in environmental security.

2. Interactive Discussion Method

This method is carried out through a question-and-answer session and discussion between the resource person and the participants. The discussion aims to:

- 1) Identifying Trantibumlinmas problems in the community;
- 2) Providing solutions to disturbances to public order;
- 3) Increase community participation in maintaining environmental security.

3. Mentoring Method

Mentoring is carried out by providing direction and motivation to the community so that they are able to:

- 1) Understanding the importance of public order;
- 2) Building public legal awareness;
- 3) Developing social cooperation and environmental security.

4. Evaluation Method

Evaluations are conducted to determine the level of public understanding of the outreach materials provided.

Evaluations are conducted through:

- 1) Live Q&A;
- 2) Participant observation;
- 3) Assessment of public understanding of Trantibumlinmas regulations.

3.5 Stages of Activity Implementation

The implementation of PKM activities is carried out through several stages as follows:

1. Preparation Stage

At this stage the following is done:

- 1) Preparation of activity proposals;
- 2) Coordination with sub-district and village officials;
- 3) Determination of activity participants;
- 4) Preparation of socialization materials;
- 5) Preparation of administration and activity facilities.

2. Implementation Stage

The implementation stages include:

- 1) Opening of activities;
- 2) Delivery of socialization materials;
- 3) Interactive discussion;
- 4) Submission of recommendations and solutions for Trantibumlinmas;
- 5) Documentation of activities.

3. Evaluation and Reporting Stage

These stages include:

- 1) Evaluation of activity results;
- 2) Preparation of PKM activity reports;
- 3) Preparation of recommendations for follow-up activities.

3.6 Data Collection Techniques

Data collection techniques in this PKM activity are carried out through:

1. Field observations of the condition of community public order and public order;
2. Interviews and discussions with activity participants;
3. Documentation of socialization activities;
4. Literature study of regulations and references related to Trantibumlinmas.

3.7 Activity Success Indicators

The success of this PKM activity is measured through:

1. Increasing public understanding regarding Home Affairs Ministerial Regulation Number 26 of 2020;
2. Increasing public awareness of the importance of public order;
3. Increased community participation in maintaining environmental security;
4. Establishing synergy between the community, sub-district government, and Satlinmas;
5. Creating a safer, more orderly and conducive social environment.

3.8 Activity Output

The expected output from this PKM activity is:

1. Increasing community capacity in implementing Trantibumlinmas;
2. Socialization of the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 26 of 2020 to the public;
3. Creating community participation in maintaining environmental security;
4. Compilation of reports on Community Service (PKM) activities;
5. Publication of activities as a form of strengthening community social education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Overview of PKM Locations

1. PROFILE OF AMPENAN DISTRICT

Ampenan District is a sub-district in the city of Mataram, West Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia. This area was once the city center of Lombok Island. To the west, it borders the Lombok Strait (the sea connecting Lombok Island and Bali). Ampenan District contains remnants of an old town, formerly the main port of Lombok. There are many villages which are the embodiment of various ethnic groups in Indonesia, including Chinese Village, Bugis Village, Malay Village, Banjar Village, Arab Village, Balinese Village, etc., so that the people here are heterogeneous and harmonious.

Meanwhile, many sources say that the term Ampenan comes from the word Ampen - Benang, which means fishing place/tool, referring to that term, it is not surprising that in ancient times Ampenan was known as a coastal area that had quite large fishery potential, so that it was later made the Main Port in the Lombok Region. Ampenan District is one of six districts in Mataram City. In 2007, the Mataram City Government expanded all districts and villages in Mataram City, dividing Ampenan District into two districts: Ampenan and Sekarbela. Furthermore, Ampenan District now encompasses 10 villages, including Taman Sari, South Ampenan, Banjar, Bintaro, Dayan Peken, North Ampenan, Pejeruk, Kebon Sari, and Pejarakan Karya. Ampenan District covers an area of 946,000 hectares, divided into sub-districts. The detailed area of Ampenan District can be seen in the following table:

Table 4.1 Data on the Area of Ampenan District in 2026

No	Ward	Area (ha)	Percentage
1	North Ampenan	249,361	26.36
2	Bintaro	81,767	8.64
3	Dayan week	53,872	5.69
4	Central Ampenan	59,000	6.24
5	Banjar	41,371	4.37
6	South Ampenan	83,921	8.87
7	Spacing of Works	73,942	7.82
8	Orange	84,538	8.94
9	Kebun Sari	57,520	6.08
10	Taman Sari	160,780	16.99
Amount		946,000	100%

Data source: Ampenan District Office 2026

Ampenan was formed based on Mataram City Regional Regulation Number 3 of 2007 concerning the Expansion of Districts and Villages in Mataram City. A District is a division of the Indonesian State's administrative territory under a Regency or City. A District is led by a Camat and is divided into several Villages. Ampenan District is divided into 10 (ten) villages that have certain territorial boundaries. Most of the residents of Ampenan District work as fishermen. The implementation of regional economic policies encourages structural, functional and cultural changes in the overall order of regional government administration. One of the essential changes is related to the position, authority, duties and functions of the Camat, because it carries out general government duties in the

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district area, especially attributive duties in the field of government coordination towards all government agencies in the district area, in this case coordinating community empowerment activities, organizing peace and order, enforcing laws and regulations, fostering the implementation of village government and carrying out other government duties in the district area.

GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION

Map of Ampenan District

Map Source: Ampenan District Office 2026

Geographically, the Ampenan District area of Mataram City has an area of 946,000 ha with the following boundaries:

- Western Boundary: Borders the Lombok Strait
- Eastern Boundary: Borders Selaparang District
- Northern Boundary: Borders Batu Layard and Gunung Sari Lobar Districts
- Southern Boundary : Borders Sekarbela District

The Ampenan District area of Mataram City consists of 10 (ten) sub-districts:

1. Taman Sari Subdistrict
2. South Ampenan Subdistrict
3. Banjar Village
4. North Ampenan Subdistrict
5. Bintaro Subdistrict
6. Dayan Peken Subdistrict
7. North Ampenan Subdistrict
8. Pejeruk Village
9. Kebon Sari Subdistrict
10. Pejarakan Karya Subdistrict

Ampenan District, Mataram City has a lowland topography.

2. GEOGRAPHICAL CONDITIONS

Based on the population census (DDK) as of December 31, 2022, the population was 93,410, consisting of 46,550 males and 46,860 females. Ampenan District is the most populous of the six districts in Mataram City.

4.2 General Overview of PKM Implementation

The Community Service (PKM) activity, themed "*Enhancing Community Capacity in Public Order and Public Order Management in Ampenan District, Mataram City*," was implemented as a form of academic contribution and community capacity building in supporting the creation of peace, public order, and community protection. This activity was carried out through collaboration between lecturers from the Institute of Public Administration (IPDN), the Ampenan District Government, and the Mataram City Civil Service Police Unit. The implementation of PKM activities aims to increase public understanding regarding the importance of public participation in maintaining environmental security, increase public knowledge regarding the concept of public order and security, and strengthen understanding regarding the duties and functions of Satpol PP and Satlinmas in implementing Trantibumlinmas. The activity was carried out in Ampenan District, Mataram City, involving community members, village officials, members of the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas), community leaders, youth leaders, and district government officials. The activity was implemented through lectures, interactive discussions, questions and answers, and the presentation of case studies related to social conditions in the Ampenan District area.

The main material in PKM activities consists of three main materials, namely:

1. The Role of the Community in Public Order by the Ampenan Sub-district Head;
2. Concept of Public Order and Peace by IPDN Lecturer;
3. Duties and Functions of Satpol PP and Satlinmas by the Mataram City Satpol PP Office.
4. The Role of Linmas in the Subdistrict Environment

4.3 Results of Activity Implementation

4.3.1 Material I: The Role of the Community in Public Order and Public Order by the Head of Ampenan District

The first presentation was delivered by the Ampenan Sub-district Head, who emphasized the importance of community involvement in maintaining environmental security and order. In his presentation, he explained that public peace and order cannot be achieved solely through the role of the government and security forces, but requires the active participation of the community as a key element in maintaining social stability. The Ampenan sub-district head explained that the community plays a strategic role in maintaining neighborhood security through night patrols, neighborhood monitoring, reporting security disturbances, and participating in community social activities. Furthermore, the community is expected to act as agents of social conflict prevention and maintain harmonious social relations in their neighborhoods. During the discussion, participants addressed various issues frequently encountered in the community, such as public order disturbances, waste issues, social conflicts between residents, and low community participation in neighborhood security activities. The discussion revealed that strengthening collective community awareness is a crucial factor in creating a safe and orderly environment. The results of the activity demonstrated an increased public understanding of the importance of social participation in the implementation of Trantibumlinmas (public order and public order). Participants began to understand that environmental safety is not solely the responsibility of the government, but a shared responsibility of all elements of society. Academically, this material demonstrates that a participatory approach to environmental security development has a significant impact on the effectiveness of maintaining public order and security. This concept aligns with the theory of community empowerment, which positions communities as the subject of development and the primary actors in maintaining social stability. The following shows an image of the presentation of material by the Ampenan District Head.

Figure 2. Presentation of Material by the Head of Ampenan District

4.3.2 Material II: Concept of Public Order and Peace by IPDN Lecturer

The second topic was presented by a lecturer from the National Institute of Public Administration (IPDN) on the concept of public order and security from the perspective of government and public administration. He explained that public order is a social condition that is safe, peaceful, and free from fear, while public order is a state of social order characterized by public compliance with applicable legal norms and regulations. The IPDN lecturer explained that maintaining public order and security is part of the mandatory government affairs related to basic services, as stipulated in Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government. Therefore, regional governments are responsible for creating conducive social conditions through policies, community development, and enforcement of regional regulations. Furthermore, it was explained that the concept of Trantibumlinmas in modern governance is not solely oriented toward a repressive approach, but also utilizes preventive, educational, and participatory approaches. This preventive approach is implemented through outreach, public education, and increasing public legal awareness. During the activity, participants demonstrated high enthusiasm for the material presented, particularly regarding the relationship between public order and everyday social life. They also understood that even minor violations of public order can impact social stability if not handled effectively. The implementation results showed an increase in participants' understanding of the concept of Trantibumlinmas and the importance of maintaining public order in community life. The public began to understand that public order is closely linked to the quality of public services, social security, and regional development. Academically, this material strengthens the concept of collaborative governance in the implementation of Trantibumlinmas, where the government and the community must work together in creating environmental security and order.

Figure 3. Presentation of Material by IPDN NTB Lecturer

4.3.3 Material III: Duties and Functions of Satpol PP and Satlinmas by the Mataram City Satpol PP Office

The third topic was presented by a resource person from the Mataram City Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) regarding the duties and functions of the Civil Service Police Unit (Satpol PP) and the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas). The speaker explained that Satpol PP is a regional agency tasked with enforcing regional regulations, maintaining public order and public safety, and providing community protection. Meanwhile, Satlinmas is explained as a community organization formed by the regional government to assist in maintaining peace, public order, community protection, and disaster management at the sub-district and community level. The resource person also explained that the Public Order Agency (Satlinmas) plays a crucial role in assisting with environmental security, community social activities, disaster mitigation, and securing government and election activities. Therefore, enhancing the capacity of Satlinmas members is crucial to supporting the effectiveness of Trantibumlinmas implementation in the regions. In practical and discussion sessions, participants were given an understanding of basic environmental security techniques, incident reporting coordination, and procedures for handling public order disturbances. They were also given an understanding of the importance of cooperation between the community, the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas), and security forces in maintaining social stability. The results of the implementation showed that participants gained a better understanding of the roles and functions of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) and the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas) in community life. They also understood the importance of synergy between stakeholders in maintaining environmental security. Academically, this material shows that the success of the implementation of Trantibumlinmas is greatly influenced by institutional capacity, community participation, and the effectiveness of coordination between government institutions and the community.

Figure 4. Presentation of material by the Head of Public Order and Public Order, Mataram Satpolpp

4.3. 4. The Role of Linmas in the Subdistrict Environment

The Community Protection Unit (Linmas) is a crucial element in maintaining peace, public order, and community protection at the lowest level, namely the sub-district. Linmas's existence not only complements security forces but also represents community participation in maintaining social stability in their communities. Normatively, the role of Linmas is regulated in Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 26 of 2020, which emphasizes that Linmas has the function of assisting local governments in maintaining public order and security, as well as protecting the community. In the context of sub-districts, this role is highly strategic because Linmas interacts directly with the community and has a deeper understanding of social conditions.

4.1 Preventive Role

Linmas plays a role in preventing disturbances to public order and security. These activities include:

- 1) Monitoring of environmental security situations
- 2) Early detection of potential social conflict
- 3) Socialization of norms and rules to the community

From the perspective of community - based security theory , this preventive role is very important because it is able to suppress potential conflicts before they develop into bigger disturbances.

4.2 Limited Repressive Role

Linmas also has a role in the initial handling of limited public order disturbances, such as:

- 1) Assisting in regulating community activities that have the potential to disrupt public order
- 2) Supporting the duties of the Civil Service Police Unit in enforcing regional regulations
- 3) Secure community activities at the sub-district level

This role is limited because Linmas is not a law enforcement officer, but rather an assistance element that works in a coordinated manner.

4.3 Participatory Role

Linmas acts as a bridge between the government and the community in creating social order. This role includes:

- 1) Encourage community participation in maintaining environmental security
- 2) Activating the neighborhood security system (siskamling)
- 3) Establish communication with community leaders and youth

According to participation theory (Sherry Arnstein), the success of community-based programs is largely determined by the level of active involvement of residents, which in this case is facilitated by Linmas.

4.4 Responsive Role in Disaster Management

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At the sub-district level, Linmas also has an important role in emergency situations, such as:

- 1) Assisting with evacuation during disasters
- 2) Providing first aid
- 3) Coordinate with relevant agencies in disaster management

This role is in line with the concept of community protection which is not only limited to security aspects, but also includes the safety of citizens from disaster risks.

4.5 The Role of Social Mediation

In heterogeneous societies such as in urban areas, Linmas often acts as a mediator in resolving social conflicts, such as:

- 1) Conflict between residents
- 2) Environmental disputes
- 3) Potential for friction between groups

Figure 5. Preparation of material by the Sub-district Secretary of Ampenan District

CONCLUSION

The role of Linmas in the sub-district environment is highly strategic and multidimensional, encompassing preventive, limited repressive, participatory, responsive, and social mediation functions. Optimizing this role requires increased capacity, policy support, and synergy between the government and the community.

Thus, Linmas not only functions as a government tool, but also as an agent of community empowerment in creating public order and peace in a sustainable manner.

4.4 Supporting and Inhibiting Factors in the Implementation of PKM

4.4.1 Supporting Factors

Several factors that support the successful implementation of PKM activities include:

1. Support from Ampenan District Government;
2. The enthusiasm of the community and activity participants;
3. Support from resource persons from IPDN and Mataram City Satpol PP;
4. There is cooperation between stakeholders;
5. Availability of facilities for implementing activities.

4.4.2 Inhibiting Factors

The inhibiting factors in implementing activities include:

1. Time limitations for implementing activities;
2. Differences in participants' level of understanding;
3. The participation of some communities in environmental security activities is still low;
4. Limited supporting facilities for Satlinmas development.

4.5 Analysis of PKM Implementation Results

The implementation of PKM activities demonstrated that an educational and participatory approach, through outreach, can increase public understanding of the importance of Trantibumlinmas (Community Safety and Public Order). These activities also demonstrated that communities have significant potential to support environmental security if provided with appropriate guidance and support. The successful implementation of this PKM activity through the socialization of the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation 26 of 2020, received attention and became a forum for brainstorming and releasing the heavy burden that had been felt by community leaders, especially the Heads of the neighborhoods in the Ampenan sub-district who were present to provide responses and ask for more attention from the city government through the sub-district government. Theoretically, the results of the activity demonstrate the relevance of community empowerment and collaborative governance theories in the implementation of Trantibumlinmas (public order and public order). The involvement of the government, community, Satpol PP (civil service police), and Satlinmas demonstrates stakeholder synergy in creating social stability. In addition, the Community Service Program (PKM) activities also demonstrate that increasing community capacity through the dissemination of Permendagri 26 of 2020 can strengthen community social resilience against security disturbances, social conflicts, and public order issues in the community.

4.6 Conclusion

The implementation of Community Service Program (PKM) in Ampenan District, Mataram City, has had a positive impact on increasing public understanding and participation in the implementation of Trantibumlinmas (public order and safety). Through the delivery of materials on the role of the community, the concept of public safety and order, and the duties and functions of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) and the Community Protection Unit (Satlinmas), the community gained a better understanding of the importance of collectively maintaining security and order in the community. This activity also strengthens the synergy between the government, the community, Satpol PP, and Satlinmas in creating a safe, orderly, and conducive environment in Ampenan District, Mataram City.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1 Conclusion

- 1) The implementation of Community Service (PKM) activities on *Increasing Community Capacity in Trantibumlinmas in Ampenan District, Mataram City* has gone well and has had a positive impact on increasing community understanding and participation in maintaining peace, public order, and community protection.
- 2) The PKM activities were conducted through three main topics: the role of the community in Trantibumlinmas (public order and security) by the Ampenan Sub-district Head, the concept of public peace and order by IPDN lecturers, and the duties and functions of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) and the Public Order Agency (Satlinmas) by the Mataram City Satpol PP Office. These three topics provided the community with a comprehensive understanding of the importance of synergy between the government, security forces, and the community in creating a safe, orderly, and conducive environment.
- 3) The results of the activities indicate that the community is beginning to understand the importance of active involvement in maintaining environmental security through social participation, environmental monitoring, and support for Satlinmas activities. Furthermore, the community has gained an understanding of the concept of Trantibumlinmas as part of public services and mandatory government affairs related to basic community services.
- 4) The implementation of Community Service Programs (PKM) also demonstrated that increasing community capacity through educational, participatory, and collaborative approaches can strengthen public awareness of the importance of public order and safety. This activity demonstrates that the success of Trantibumlinmas implementation is greatly influenced by stakeholder synergy, effective community development, and active community participation in maintaining social and environmental stability.

Thus, this PKM activity can be a form of strengthening the social capacity of the community in supporting the creation of environmental security, increasing the social resilience of the community, and strengthening the role of Satlinmas and local government in implementing Trantibumlinmas in Ampenan District, Mataram City.

5.2 Suggestions

Based on the results of the implementation of PKM activities, there are several suggestions that can be used as recommendations, namely as follows:

1. The Ampenan District Government is expected to continue to improve community development and empowerment in the field of public order and security through ongoing outreach, training, and community assistance activities.
2. The Mataram City Civil Service Police Unit is expected to increase the capacity of Satlinmas members through technical education and training related to environmental security, disaster mitigation, and handling public order disturbances.
3. The community is expected to participate more actively in maintaining environmental security through night patrols, reporting security disturbances, and involvement in social activities.
4. It is necessary to increase synergy between the local government, Satpol PP, TNI, Polri, community leaders, and community organizations in supporting the implementation of Trantibumlinmas in the Ampenan District area.
5. Universities, especially IPDN, are expected to continue to carry out community service activities as a form of academic contribution in supporting social development and increasing the capacity of local communities.
6. There is a need for a more applicable and sustainable follow-up program so that the increase in community capacity in the field of Trantibumlinmas can continue to develop and have a real impact on creating a safe, orderly, and conducive community environment.

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REFERENCES

- Adisasmita, R. (2006). *Pembangunan pedesaan dan perkotaan*. Graha Ilmu.
- Adisasmita, R. (2011). *Manajemen pemerintahan daerah*. Graha Ilmu.
- Chambers, R. (1997). *Whose reality counts? Putting the first last*. Intermediate Technology Publications.
- Cohen, J. M., & Uphoff, N. T. (1980). *Participation's place in rural development*. Cornell University Press.
- Dye, T. R. (1992). *Understanding public policy*. Prentice Hall.
- Edwards III, G. C. (1980). *Implementing public policy*. Congressional Quarterly Press.
- Friedmann, J. (1992). *Empowerment: The politics of alternative development*. Blackwell Publishers.
- Hikmat, H. (2010). *Strategi pemberdayaan masyarakat*. Humaniora.
- Ife, J. (2008). *Community development*. Pustaka Pelajar.
- Ife, J., & Tesoriero, F. (2008). *Community development: Community-based alternatives in an age of globalization*. Pearson Education.
- Kartasmita, G. (1996). *Pembangunan untuk rakyat: Memadukan pertumbuhan dan pemerataan*. CIDES.
- Kansil, C. S. T. (2005). *Pengantar ilmu hukum dan tata hukum Indonesia*. Balai Pustaka.
- Korten, D. C. (1990). *Getting to the 21st century: Voluntary action and the global agenda*. Kumarian Press.
- Mardikanto, T. (2010). *Konsep-konsep pemberdayaan masyarakat*. UNS Press.
- Midgley, J. (1995). *Social development: The developmental perspective in social welfare*. Sage Publications.
- Morgan, P. (2006). *The concept of capacity*. European Centre for Development Policy Management (ECDPM).
- Ndraha, T. (2003). *Kybernology: Ilmu pemerintahan baru*. Rineka Cipta.
- Ostrom, E. (1990). *Governing the commons: The evolution of institutions for collective action*. Cambridge University Press.
- Pretty, J. (1995). *Participatory learning for sustainable agriculture*. IIED.
- Putnam, R. D. (1993). *Making democracy work: Civic traditions in modern Italy*. Princeton University Press.
- Soekanto, S. (2012). *Sosiologi suatu pengantar*. Rajawali Pers.
- Soetomo. (2011). *Pemberdayaan masyarakat: Konsep dan implementasi*. Pustaka Pelajar.
- Suharto, E. (2014). *Membangun masyarakat memberdayakan rakyat*. Refika Aditama.
- Sumodiningrat, G. (1999). *Pemberdayaan masyarakat dan jaring pengaman sosial*. Gramedia.

Todaro, M. P. (2000). *Economic development*. Addison Wesley.

Winarno, B. (2012). *Kebijakan publik: Teori, proses, dan studi kasus*. CAPS.

World Bank. (2002). *Empowerment and poverty reduction: A sourcebook*. World Bank.

B. Jurnal Ilmiah

Adelia, R., Putri, S., & Rahman, F. (2025). Ketertiban umum dan dinamika sosial perkotaan. *Jurnal Pembangunan dan Kebijakan Publik*, 11(1).

Gunawan. (2015). Peran satuan perlindungan masyarakat dalam menjaga ketertiban dan keamanan lingkungan. *Jurnal Administrasi Publik*, 3(1).

Hamudy, M. I. A. (2014). Eksistensi satuan perlindungan masyarakat dalam penyelenggaraan ketertiban umum. *Jurnal Bina Praja*, 6(3).

Ma'ruf, M. (2023). Sinergitas stakeholder dalam penyelenggaraan ketentraman dan ketertiban umum. *Jurnal Governance*, 8(1).

Saudi, A. (2023). Strategi komunikasi satuan polisi pamong praja dalam penegakan peraturan daerah. *Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi*, 7(1).

Simarmata, T. H. (2022). Strategi satuan polisi pamong praja dalam penegakan ketertiban umum. *Jurnal Administrasi Negara*, 10(2).

Ummatullah, A. Z. (2019). Kedudukan satuan perlindungan masyarakat dalam sistem ketatanegaraan Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan*, 4(2).

Winarko, A. D. (2024). Pemberdayaan satlinmas dalam meningkatkan ketahanan sosial masyarakat. *Jurnal Community Development*, 9(2).

C. Dokumen Resmi / Regulasi

Kementerian Dalam Negeri. (2020). *Peraturan Menteri Dalam Negeri Nomor 26 Tahun 2020 tentang penyelenggaraan ketertiban umum dan ketentraman masyarakat serta perlindungan masyarakat*. Kemendagri.

Republik Indonesia. (1945). *Undang-Undang Dasar Negara Republik Indonesia Tahun 1945*.

Republik Indonesia. (2014). *Undang-Undang Nomor 23 Tahun 2014 tentang pemerintahan daerah*. Sekretariat Negara.

Republik Indonesia. (2018). *Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 16 Tahun 2018 tentang satuan polisi pamong praja*. Sekretariat Negara.

Pemerintah Kota Mataram. (2015). *Peraturan Daerah Kota Mataram Nomor 11 Tahun 2015 tentang ketenteraman dan ketertiban di Kota Mataram*.

Pemerintah Kota Mataram. (2017). *Peraturan Wali Kota Mataram Nomor 26 Tahun 2017 tentang petunjuk pelaksanaan Peraturan Daerah Kota Mataram Nomor 11 Tahun 2015*.

D. Laporan / Organisasi Internasional

UNDP. (2009). *Capacity development: A UNDP primer*. United Nations Development Programme.

UNDP. (2009). *Human development report*. United Nations Development Programme.